

AN INNOVATIVE RAFT TO BOOST THE MOLLUSK FARMING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This document describes the advantages of a new floating raft for the harvest of mussels, oysters and other types of molluscs. The platform is made of an Ultra-High-Performance Fibre Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC, named in this document UHC) developed by the company Research & Development Concretes SL (RDC in advance) and registered as Formex®.

The solution provides advantages in terms of reduction of risks for the employees, environmental impact, competitiveness of the business and potential synergies with other sectors (tourism, weather forecasts, alerts, marine energy), and four of them have been already installed in the context of the H2020 Phase 2 project SELMUS-738777. In this document, many of their advantages are evaluated and a comparison is made with the wooden raft and the longline system in terms of viability of the business.

1. Introduction

In the period 2005-2015 the European mussel production has decreased by 16%, while it grew in the rest of the world by 20% [2]. Many EU farming regions almost didn't renovate and their competitiveness has declined. However, Europe has a mussel tradition and outstanding coastal conditions for its farming. In fact, Spain is the 3rd top world producer with a 45% of the EU mussels and directly employing 11,500 people. This document proposes and innovative offshore structure for mussel farming (raft) which aims to boost the competitiveness of this sector.

Mussel farming systems depend on the oceanic conditions and the traditions. In Spain, South Africa and the US the raft farming system is used, being the predominant system in the first country. The system is used in the regions that are protected from relevant swell, as estuaries or salty lakes. The most common is not to find a reduced number of rafts, as the tools and equipment used to carry out the business imply an investment that is only amortized when the business is scaled with certain number of units. The development of a raft that can resist the effect of a more intense swell would open this efficient system to many other regions and decrease the investment required in refurbishment. The Formex® raft has reached the market to solve this and other problems.

Figure 1. Group of eucalyptus rafts for mussel farming in the Vigo estuary (Galicia, Spain)

The other main farming systems used in Europe are the French bouchot and the longline. The first is mainly used in France, being its use only possible in regions with a relevant tidal range and wide extensions for the harvest. The longline is more extended and it is used mainly in opened waters or partially protected waters, where the wooden raft is not able to resist the swell or where its agitation would imply a relevant loss of mussel. An improved raft as the proposed here opens the door for this system to be used in the regions where waters are partially protected and where the longline is nowadays the only option for the farmers. The map of figure 2 shows the main mussel farming regions in the EU regions and the number of rafts that would be used to equal the current production in the case that the raft system was used.

Figure 2. Main farming systems in Europe and number of rafts that would be needed to harvest the current production

2. The traditional wooden raft

A traditional wooden raft is a grid of 20 x 27 m (540 m²) formed generally by 4 to 6 main beams connected to 4 to 6 polyester-coated steel floaters, 11 secondary beams supported orthogonally on the main beams. It has wooden joists supported orthogonally on the secondary beams and separated a distance between 0.6 and 1 m, depending on the traditions of each region and the producer. The lightship weight of a wooden raft ranges between 40 and 65 t. The main geometrical parameters of the elements are:

nº	Element	Units per raft	Geometry	Depth (m)	Width (m)	Length (m)	Weight/unit
1	Steel floaters	4 to 6	Cylindrical	∅ 2 to 2.4	-	3.5 to 5.5	2.3 to 3.5 t
2	Primary beams	4 to 6	Square	0.35 to 0.4	0.35 to 0.4	20	1.9 to 2.5
3	Secondary beams	10 to 12	Square	0.25 to 0.35	0.25 to 0.35	27	1.3 to 2.6
4	joists	25 to 40	rectangular	0.07 to 0.1	0.08 to 0.12	20	0.12 to 0.2
5	Harvest	500 ropes	-	-	-	12 (rope)	Up to 80 t

Figure 3. Description of the main elements of the most common wooden raft. Photo: Lufort-RDC

The use of wood in these offshore structures has its origin in the beginning of century XX, when the wooden hull of the ships was used for that purpose. Besides its mechanical strength, wood fulfils the following requirements:

- Reduced weight: The smaller the weight of the structure, the smaller the investment in floaters.
- High flexibility: the lower the stiffness of the structure, the higher the adaptation to the swell, and the lower the pull out of the mussel due to the vertical displacement of the rope.
- Easiness to drill and connect elements, facilitating the assembling of the beams and joists that compose the raft.

Wood has been traditionally used as no other material was found combining this lightness, robustness, and flexibility to adapt to swells. In countries where farming is carried out in opened waters, less intensive systems are used, as in the raft the damages of the connections are too frequent due to the intensity of the swell, so the lifetime is too reduced. This shows that in the last decades there has been a clear need of a durable, reliable and sustainable raft for different water conditions. In 2014 the materials engineering firm RDC designed an offshore floating raft made of Ultra High Performance Fiber Reinforced Concrete. The company IDIFOR (founded by RDC with the Spanish precast concrete company Lufort) manufactured it for first time in 2016 and at this moment already four elements are floating in Spain.

4. Development of a UHC raft: The Formex® raft

The Formex® rafts are designed with a UHC (Formex®) which rheological and mechanical characterization can be found at [1]. The design of the elements that compose the raft was conditioned by the following aspects:

1. Design an element with similar surface than the wooden rafts, and with similar farming tools and equipment that those used nowadays.
2. Minimize the total weight of the structure and maintain the same floating system.
3. Minimize the number of different elements, in order to maximize the level of industrialization, favor the production of the precast elements and simplify the assembling.
4. The UHC beams should have a stiffness comparable to the wooden beams in order to avoid the pull-out of the mussels from the ropes.

Following these requirements, two different types of rafts were designed. The first (named Formex®Mixta raft) was developed to substitute the main and secondary wooden beams to enhance their durability. The wooden joists have been conserved from the traditional raft. The second and most advanced raft is the so-called Formex®Plus, which is completely made of UHC (Formex®) and which is conceived to provide a flat surface to facilitate the work of the farmers and is conceived as a structure that allows farming in less protected waters.

The Utility Model of both fiber-reinforced concrete rafts for mollusc farming was granted in March 2016 (Publication no.: ES 1147609 U), and it has been requested for France, Italy and Chile.

4.1. The Formex® Mixta raft: A durable standard UHC raft

The structural scheme of the raft is completely similar to the traditional wooden raft: The six primary beams are independent and connected to the six floaters, the 11 secondary beams are orthogonally connected to them with 22 mm of diameter steel bolts. The wooden joists are connected orthogonally on the secondary beams. In this model of raft, the main improvement of the use of UHC is the enhancement of durability of the structural beams.

In the traditional solution, the wood is screwed during the assembling process to do the connection. In UHC the screw has been avoided for the high concentration of prestressing steel. Instead, a notched cuboid element of polyethylene 1000 (density=1000 kg/m³) was employed in the formwork before the fabrication of the precast beams (see figure 4). During the assembling of the raft, this element was drilled in the adequate location, providing a tolerance of ±4 cm in each direction.

Figure 4: Connection system of the traditional wooden raft (left); connection system of the UHC raft (right)

The comparison between the beams that compose the traditional and the UHC rafts is shown as follows:

Element	Wooden elements (typical values)		UHC Formex® Mixta raft	
	Dimensions (m)	Weight/unit (t)	Dimensions (m)	Weight/unit (t)
Primary beams	0.35x0.35, 20 m	2.4	0.35x0.225, 20 m	Lighted. 3.1 t
Secondary beams	0.3x0.3, 27 m	2	0.25x0.225, 27 m	Lighted. 3.05 t
Total weight raft (without floaters)	44 t		59 t	

Thus, with UHC the total thickness of the raft is reduced from 0.65 m to 0.45 m. Figure 5 shows the primary and secondary UHC beams produced for the first Formex® Mixta raft. The upper surface is textured to prevent slippage. Figure 5 shows the grid performed with the Formex® beams down the wooden joists.

Figure 5. Formex® Mixta raft floating in O Grove, Pontevedra, Galicia (Spain)

Figure 6. Left: Surface finishing of a secondary beam of the Formex® Mixta raft. Right: Formex® Mixta raft floating in its final position with a camera control in O Grove, Pontevedra, Galicia (Spain)

Figure 7. Formex® Mixta floating in O Grove, Ria de Arousa (Spain). The photo was obtained with a drone

4.2. The Formex® Plus raft: A durable flat UHC raft for opened waters

This solution is an improved design of the geometry of the traditional raft. It is conceived for especially aggressive swell conditions or/and to increase the productiveness of the sector (see [1]). The main difference is that the raft is completely flat, its total depth is more reduced and it does not have wood, so the maintenance is minimum. The wooden joists of the Formex® Mixta are here integrated as UHC joists connecting the secondary beams, composing UHC frames (figure 8, right).

Figure 8. From left to right: Joists of the wooden raft, of the Formex® Mixta raft and of the Formex® Plus raft

The UHC joist was designed to provide the same capacity as the wooden joists. As the secondary beams, the wooden joists were submitted to flexural tests to evaluate their capacity in bending (see [1]). The bending tests were carried out for two different joists with section 100 x 80 mm (width x depth) with a span of 2 m. The tests carried out to evaluate the capacity of the wooden and UHC joists can be found in [1].

The advantages of the integration of the UHC joist with the beams is that the pulling out of the nail is avoided, the assembling is much faster because of the reduction in number of elements to connect and the final surface is completely flat, increasing the operational safety and allows installing platforms with rails that facilitate the work.

The design of the Formex®Plus also modifies the six primary beams (2 per floater) for three frames (1 per floater), connecting the primary beams to facilitate the assembling and to reduce the curvature of the secondary beams. The secondary beams are substituted by 5 secondary frames of 27 meters of length that are supported orthogonally on the primary frames and spaced 2 meters. In the spacing, three shorter frames with a similar width are placed and supported between the spacing of the 27 m-length frames (figure 9). The total weight of this system is of 83 t. The following photos show the grid performed with the frames in a Formex®Plus prototype performed in Vasc Country (Spain). The dimensions of this platform were 13.2 x 27 m. During October of 2017 a 20 x 27 m Formex®Plus raft will be installed in Galicia.

Figure 9. Process of assembling of a Formex®Plus raft for Mutriku port, Vasc Country (Spain)

The comparison between the beams that compose the traditional and the UHC rafts is shown as follows:

Element	Wooden elements (typical values)		UHC Formex®Plus elements	
	Dimensions (m)	Weight/unit (t)	Dimensions (m)	Weight/unit (t)
Primary beams	0.35x0.35, 20 m	2.4	Frame, 2x0.35x0.225, 20 m. 3 units	Lighted. 8 t
Secondary beams	0.3x0.3, 27 m	2	Frame with joists, 27 m	Lighted. 0.14 t/m ²
Total weight raft (without floaters)	44 t		83 t	

4.3. The Formex® Oyster raft: A UHC raft with elevable frames optimized for oyster farming

This solution is an adaptation of the mussel Formex® rafts to optimize the oyster farming. The platform is flat and completely made of Formex®, and the design is separated in two corridors of 3 m of width in the external sides and the farming region in the center and divided in 13 frames. These frames can be raised up to 3 meters to extract the ropes with oysters, facilitating the works and the drying and falling of the epiphytes. The raft has capacity to produce 20 ton/year of oysters and it is a special solution designed for the oyster harvest sector. The first prototype of Formex® oyster raft has been installed in the port of Valencia for the company Ostras de Valencia SL.

Figure 10. View of the farming frames of the Formex® Oyster raft

Figure 11. View of the farming frames of the Formex® Oyster raft after the installation of the rail to rise the frames

Figure 12. Launching of the Formex® Oyster raft to the water in the Valencia port

Figure 13. Formex® Oyster raft near a traditional oyster farming raft in Valencia port

5. Comparison between different systems in a mussel farm

In the following lines is compared a mussel farm with a capacity of approximately 400 t/year using the long longline system, the wooden raft system, the Formex® Mixta raft system and the Formex® Plus raft system. The hypothesis made is that the farm is situated in waters submitted to a medium-low intensity of swell (protected or semi-protected waters). The comparison is made in terms of environmental impact, safety, operational aspects, competitiveness of the system and alignment of the solution with the EU strategies.

5.1. Environmental aspects

The relevant environmental factors considered are:

Surface of sea occupied: Each of the systems is occupying certain sheet of water per kg produced. In the case of the wooden rafts, the average production per wooden raft in Galicia for the last 7 years is 67.8 t, so considering that the number of rafts in Galicia is 3.337 and their surface is 20 x 27 m the average production is 126.6 kg/m². In the case of the long line is approximately 100 t/ha [3], which implies 10 kg/m². This much higher occupation of the sea for the long line implies:

1. The intrusion with shipping, yachting, fishing sites, tourism and beaches for swimming can be much higher. For that reason, the European Commission has set the maritime spatial planning as one of the main components of the Blue Growth strategy.

2. The acceptance of mussel cultivation plants in coastal areas can be lower due to the aesthetic problems by visual intrusion (buoyage on surface).
3. The longline creates a long barrier, which endanger large vertebrates and fishes by possible entanglement.
4. The larger the line of harvest, the higher the costs to protect from predators. In the case of rafts, the method is a rectangular net with a perimeter of less than 100 meters. In the case of longline, the protection required is much longer.
5. As will be explained afterwards, the business need to be scaled up to be economically efficient, and the access to wide and protected spaces is a critical limiting factor [4].

The carbon footprint: The carbon footprint is here compared considering the production of farming main investments (ropes, buoys, pegs, rafts, floaters...) distributed along their lifetime expected, and the farm operations (electricity and fuel).

The use of ropes in the raft has been reduced a 40% compared to the longlines because the absence of the horizontal dropper lines. For the evaluation of the CO₂ of the wooden raft it has been considered that the efficiency of an eucalyptus globulus forest is of 30 m³ per hectare sewed [6], which implies that to produce a raft (48 m³ of wood) 1.6 ha of forest are sewed. As a eucalyptus forest captures 20 to 25 t of CO₂/ha/year [6], this implies that the capture of 36 t of CO₂ per year is prevented. It has been considered that the period that the eucalyptus wood forest requires to renew is 8 years, so the construction of each wooden rafts imply to avoid the capture of 288 t of CO₂. The average production for each raft has been considered 67.8 t/year, and the wooden raft lifetime 12 years.

For the Formex[®] raft, according to international publications the CO₂ emission of a m³ of the material has been considered 1.35 t. The Formex[®] Plus raft lifetime has been considered 40 years. The steel of the floaters has been counted with an emission of 1.9 t of CO₂/t of steel, and it is smaller for the wooden raft because the Formex[®] raft requires around 20% more of buoyancy to float.

Finally, the CO₂ footprint is highly dependent on the fuel consumed, which for the rafts is considered to be 50% of the amount consumed with the longline system due to the much shorter distance that has to be done for the farming process, as the raft concentrates all the ropes in a platform and not along kilometers of line. The following table summarizes the CO₂ balance and shows that the Formex[®] raft is the system with the lowest footprint per ton of mussel harvested.

Concept	Element	Longline	wooden raft	Formex [®] Plus raft	
Material production	Ropes [5]	42.6	21.3	21.3	kgCO ₂ -eq/t of mussel produced
Material production	Buoys [5]	17.7	0	0	
Material production	Pegs [5]	14.2	0	0	
Material production	Mesh socks [5]	19.1	19.1	19.1	
Material production	raft (20x27 m)	0	354	16.0	
Material production	steel floaters	0	10.6	12.7	
Material production	TOTAL	93.60	404.93	69.07	
Farm operations	electricity use [5]	33.7	33.7	33.7	
Farm operations	fuel use [5]	105	63	63	
Farm operations	TOTAL	138.70	96.70	96.70	
Material+operations	TOTAL	232	502	166	

The maintenance products: The wood is organic and it requires the use of maintenance products to increase the lifetime of the wooden raft. However, the European Directives are more and more restrictive with this and many of the traditional protection procedures cannot be applied nowadays or will be forbidden in a medium term because they alter the ecosystem of the estuaries.

The following table resumes the environmental aspects of the systems compared:

Factor	Unit	Longline	Wooden raft	Formex®Plus raft
Production/m ²	Kg/m ² occupied	10	126.6	126.6
Carbon footprint	kgCO ₂ -eq/t of mussel	232	502	166
Protection products		No	required	No

5.2. Safety and operational aspects

Safety during assembling: The installation of farming systems described is very different. In the case of the longline the procedure is standard and must be done using a complementary ship to launch progressively the linear farm. The risks associated to this process are relatively low. In the case of the wooden raft, the typical assembling procedure in Spain is made manually and inefficiently through a high-risk job in the inter-tidal zone using hammers and nails. The working high is of 3.5 meters and generally, no restraint systems are used. In the case of the Formex® raft this problem is solved, as the elements are modular and the work is performed in the port, where the use of restraint systems is much easier (life-line).

Safety during operations: The procedure of farming and harvesting in the longline requires a work performed from the border of the ship and in contact with the ropes, which imply a medium risk of falling to the water. The wooden raft has also a medium risk of falling or stumble because the elements that compose the platform are in three different heights, because sometimes the wood is almost rotten and can suffer a brittle failure and because the surface slips due to the presence of algae. The Formex® raft is a flat and inorganic platform, so these last three factors are not present. Besides, the surface is rough to minimize the risk of falling.

Assembling time: A farm of 70 t requires the launching of approximately 700 m of longline. The installation of 100 m of line require approximately half working day. The assembling of a wooden raft requires generally 2 days and to wait the assembling until the days before the rising tide. In the case of the Formex® raft, the assembling requires 2 days and does not depend on the tides. Precast modules are fast and safe and do not require nails.

Time of response from the provider: In the case of the longline the time to order delivery can be very reduced because there are standard elements, exactly as the Formex® raft (max 2 weeks). In the case of the wooden raft, the time can be up to 6 weeks because the assembler company needs to fell and treat the trees that are adequate for the requirements of the customer.

Factor	Unit	Longline	Wooden raft	Formex® raft
Safety assembling	risk	Low	high	low
Safety operational	risk	medium	medium	low
Assembling time	days	2 lines/day (20 t/day) [7]	2 days (34 t/day)	2 days (34 t/day)
Time to order delivery	time	reduced	Up to 6 weeks	reduced (<2 weeks)

5.3. Alignment with EU strategies

The Formex® raft proposed in this document is a relevant innovation in terms of equipment to develop a competitive marine aquaculture. It is clearly aligned with the three components of the EU Blue Growth strategy:

1. In recent years the EU aquaculture sector has been stagnant. As it will be shown in the next subchapter, the raft proposed herein boosts productivity and improves mussel aquaculture competitiveness, a sector with a high potential for sustainable jobs, growth and exports.
2. The Formex® raft improves the **marine knowledge, the maritime spatial planning and the integrated maritime surveillance**. It does this by ordering cultivation on an efficient, intensive, controlled and visible 540 m² platform. To reach a similar production some regions mix different methods, use a tangle of

kilometres of submerged ropes (longline method), or set linear intrusive barriers along the coast, such as the French bouchot. The Formex® raft facilitates access to information through inspections or the installation of control devices. In fact, some of the Formex® rafts that are already in service broadcast live and open in internet the weather conditions. This can be followed in the YouTube channel of the company IDIFOR: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCc5JcG4j3GEZDAUAWXzUj-g>

3. The Formex® raft reduces considerable the footprint of other methods and avoids the felling of trees with high environmental value that is required to assemble a traditional wooden raft.

Furthermore, the Formex® raft meet the challenges set in the 10-year growth strategy Europe 2020: it delivers high productivity, employment, and social cohesion through its three mutual priorities to change the EU economy. More precisely it supports:

1. Smart growth: Competitiveness is boosted as production is faster and industrialised. It is clearly the most economical solution in the mid and long term (see next subchapter).
2. Sustainable growth: the EU promotes a resource-efficient, greener and competitive economy (Art. 1-3, EU Constitutional Treaty). The Formex® raft minimizes the resources consumed, CO2 emissions, and avoids the use of toxic protective products (aligned with the EU Coastal and Marine Policy).
3. Inclusive growth: The Formex® raft reduces production costs of a sector that has been declining for years. Recovery will launch employment and will contribute to the territorial cohesion of the regions that have traditionally depended on the sea.

Thus, the Formex® raft fits within the frame of the EU searched low-carbon economy and puts EU on an upward path of prosperity and sustainable recovery.

5.3. Competitiveness aspects: A business case for each farming system

In this document is compared the business viability of an installation to produce 400 t of mussel/year. This implies a farm of 4-ha of longlines according with the production rate of 100 t/ha [3], and in the case of using rafts it can be produced with a farm composed by a group of 6 rafts considering the average efficiency of production of the period 2010-2016 in Galicia region (67.8 t/raft), which imply a production of 407 t of mussel/year. For the three types of raft proposed here (wooden, Formex®Mixta and Formex®Plus) the production per year and unit has been estimated to be similar as there are not differences in the amount of harvest produced up to this moment.

The capital expenditures (CAPEX) of a 4-ha mussel longline farm in the Mediterranean Sea is based on the data present in [3], where the amortization years have been modified for few of the elements. The depreciation per year is indicated in the last line. The amortization costs per year of the longline system are the most reduced of all the systems proposed here.

Concept	4 ha long-line	Years of amort.	Cost/year
Licensing	4,000 €	1	€ 4,000
Moorings	57,200 €	10	€ 5,720
Ropes	45,570 €	8	€ 5,696
Floats	10,000 €	8	€ 1,250
Raft	- €	8	€ -
joists	- €	8	€ -
Floater	- €	8	€ -
Lighthouses	13,600 €	8	€ 1,700
Working vessel	140,000 €	12	€ 11,667
Working boat	6,000 €	8	€ 750
Outboard engine (20hp)	4,000 €	8	€ 500
car	21,000 €	8	€ 2,625
grading machine line	39,600 €	8	€ 4,950
TOTAL/year	340,970 €		€ 38,858

In the case of a farm with 6 wooden rafts, the fix investment is higher mainly because of the structure, which cost is of 55.000 €/unit and their lifetime is of only 12 years. The CAPEX in the working vessel is 40% slower because it is not required a special vessel for the development of the works.

Concept	wooden raft	Years of amort.	Cost/year
Licensing	1,000 €	1	1,000 €
Moorings	21,000 €	20	1,050 €
Ropes	45,000 €	20	2,250 €
Floats	- €	1	- €
Raft	360,000 €	12	30,000 €
joists	- €	1	- €
Floater	78,000 €	25	3,120 €
Lighthouses	- €	1	- €
Working vessel	100,000 €	12	8,333 €
Working boat	6,000 €	8	750 €
Outboard engine (20hp)	4,000 €	8	500 €
car	21,000 €	8	2,625 €
grading machine line	39,600 €	8	4,950 €
TOTAL/year	675,600 €		€ 54,578

The CAPEX of a farm with 6 Formex® Mixta rafts imply a higher initial investment, but the Formex® elements have a higher lifespan (30 years), so the amortization of the main structure per year is lower than for the wooden rafts. The joists, which are the wooden top elements, have 12 years of lifespan, as the wooden rafts.

Concept	Formex® Mixta	Years of amort.	Cost/year
Licensing	1,000 €	1	1,000 €
Moorings	21,000 €	20	1,050 €
Ropes	45,000 €	20	2,250 €
Floats	- €	1	- €
Raft	540,000 €	30	18,000 €
joists	5,000 €	12	417 €
Floater	84,000 €	25	3,360 €
Lighthouses	- €	1	- €
Working vessel	100,000 €	12	8,333 €
Working boat	6,000 €	8	750 €
Outboard engine (20hp)	4,000 €	8	500 €
car	21,000 €	8	2,625 €
grading machine line	39,600 €	8	4,950 €
TOTAL/year	866,600 €		€ 43,235

Finally, the initial CAPEX of a farm with 6 Formex® Plus rafts is the highest of all the evaluated here, but higher durability (40 years of lifespan) of the investment imply an amortization per year which is very similar to the Formex® Mixta rafts and more reduced than the wooden rafts.

Concept	Formex® raft	Years of amort.	Cost/year
Licensing	1,000 €	1	1,000 €
Moorings	21,000 €	20	1,050 €
Ropes	45,000 €	20	2,250 €
Floats	- €	1	- €
Raft	750,000 €	40	18,750 €
joists	- €	1	- €
Floaters	96,000 €	25	3,840 €
Lighthouses	- €	1	- €
Working vessel	100,000 €	12	8,333 €
Working boat	6,000 €	8	750 €
Outboard engine (20hp)	4,000 €	8	500 €
car	21,000 €	8	2,625 €
grading machine line	39,600 €	8	4,950 €
TOTAL/year	1,083,600 €		€ 44,048

The last line of the previous tables has provided the value of the annual depreciation costs of the fix investment. The operational expenditures (OPEX) are indicated as follows. For the case of the longline they were obtained from [3]. The income of the business is obtained considering a price of 0.55 €/kg (the average value in a serie of years in the Spanish market, [8]) and the profit tax rate considered has been 25%.

As can be observed, the operational costs of the raft farming system are lower than for the longline, mainly due to a lower labor costs (30% to 55% more reduced than for the longline) and lower expenses in energy (60% less) and consumables (60% to 90% lower). The reason for the reductions is that a longline installation of 4 ha has approximately 4 km of ropes and boys, being considerably higher the maintenance and the expenses in inspections [7]. The stocking of the longline system requires approximately 1 day of work every 6 lines, and the harvesting 1 day per line. The maintenance is performed every two weeks and in a day 12 lines can be done [7]. The consumables for the raft farms are much lower because the number of elements exposed to the swell and to predators is much higher in the longline farms.

Thus, despite that the initial investment is 2.5 to 3 times higher for the Formex® rafts, the operational costs are 20% to 35% lower, which implies that it is the most profitable system for this farm size (400 t/year) and price of mussel in the market (0.55 €/kg).

Concept	4 ha longline	6 wooden rafts	6 Formex® Mixta	6 Formex® Plus
depreciation	38,858 €	54,578 €	43,235 €	44,048 €
Annual fee for sea rental	4,000 €	1,000 €	1,000 €	1,000 €
energy	6,000 €	2,000 €	2,000 €	2,000 €
labour cost	50,000 €	35,000 €	35,000 €	22,500 €
consumables	10,000 €	4,000 €	2,000 €	1,000 €
insurance	500 €	500 €	500 €	500 €
maintenance service	4,000 €	3,000 €	2,000 €	500 €
others	7,000 €	7,000 €	7,000 €	7,000 €
Total costs/year	120,358 €	107,078 €	92,735 €	78,548 €
Production	400 t	407 t	407 t	407 t
income (€) (0.55 €/kg)	220,000 €	223,850 €	223,850 €	223,850 €
profit (€)	99,642 €	116,772 €	131,115 €	145,302 €
net profit (€)	74,732 €	87,579 €	98,336 €	108,976 €
net profit (%)	34.0%	39.1%	43.9%	48.7%

As a conclusion, the Formex® raft farm to produce 407 t of mussel/year is more profitable than the farm with wooden rafts or the longline farm, mainly due to the longer lifespan and lower maintenance and operative expenses.

The Net Present Value (NPV) of the investment has been obtained after 10, 15, 20 and 30 years from the initial investment and assuming a discount rate of 1.5% considering the current situation of the economy. The values of NPV at different periods are shown in the figure 14. As the investment in the longline farm are smaller and the operating costs higher, the NPV is only higher than for the raft systems for a period up to 15 years.

Figure 14. Evolution of the NPV for different years

The Internal Rate of Return at 15 years has been obtained and is present in the following table. It is also indicated the payback considering the price of mussel of 0.55 €/kg, which implies the time required to pay the investment with the gross profit generated by the business. Finally, it is indicated the critical price to obtain a profit of 0 € at the end of the year. The more reduced this value, the higher the efficiency of the system and the higher the business stability. In the case the Formex®Plus raft is showing that the business model can support prices up to 0.2 €/kg. According to this, the longline system is the less competitive for this farm size.

For price of 0.55 €/kg	4 ha longline	6 wooden rafts	6 Formex®Mixta	6 Formex®Plus
IRR15 (%)	28.55%	15.22%	14.31%	10.35%
Payback (years)	3.8	6.3	6.2	8.2
Price of mussel for profit=0	0.3 €/kg	0.263 €/kg	0.228 €/kg	0.193 €/kg

It is also relevant to evaluate through a sensibility analysis the relation between payback (time required to pay the initial investment with the profit generated) and the price of mussel/kg. This relation is shown at figure 15:

Figure 15. Relation between the price of mussel in the market and the payback of each type of farm

The figure shows that with high price of mussel in the market the investment is paid in less than 6 years for every system, being the minimum payback for the longline farm. For lower prices of the mussel (<0.4 €/kg) the payback is more reduced for the raft system than for the longline. This shows that the raft system minimizes the risk for the investor in relation with the price fluctuations.

6. Conclusions

An innovative composite named Formex® is being used to build high durability floating rafts for mussel and oyster farming. This system is demonstrating its advantages compared with the wooden raft, as they require only a minimum maintenance and provide longer lifespan, more safety and higher resistance to intense swell. The long line system is used in opened waters for its capacity to adapt to a more intense swell. For semi-opened waters, the Formex® raft can be competitive compared to the longline system, which requires a CAPEX up to 3 times lower but has higher operative expenses (30 to 55%). This imply that in normal conditions the longline farm has the lowest payback, but in a market with low price of mussel the margins can be negative while the Formex® raft system is providing positive profit due to the minimum operative expenses.

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